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From Coupling Map to Optimal Initial Layout: A Subgraph Isomorphism Approach for IBM Quantum Devices

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Noise-Aware Initial Layout Selection Using
VF2 and Linear Error Metrics on Heavy-Hex
Architectures.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The initial arrangement of logical qubits onto physical qubits is the first step in the compilation flow for noise-tolerant quantum computing. Erroneously choosing a suboptimal arrangement of this mapping negatively impacts the number of required swaps, the depth of the circuit after the assignment, and therefore the fidelity of the execution. In noisy intermediate-sized (NISQ) devices, the coherence lifetime is short, so accumulating a small reduction in fidelity means that the results end up being statistically less significant or become random noise.

The problem encountered at the Qiskit Summer School 2025 is formalized below, and the geometric noise limitations inherent to IBM's heavy-hex architecture QPUs, which motivate the use of subgraph isomorphism-based techniques, are discussed.

1.1 Initial Layout Problem Statement

Let $G_L = (V_L, E_L)$ be the logical graph that describes the interactions of two qubits (edges) and the logical qubits (vertices) of an abstract quantum circuit. For the class of fermionic algorithms (e.g., quantum chemistry), G_L typically has a chain or zig-zag structure with $|V_L| = n_{\text{orbitals}} + n_{\text{rings}}$.

Let $G_P = (V_P, E_P, w_q, w_e)$ be the physical graph of the backend, where V_P is the set of physical qubits; E_P is the set of gated-coupled pairs (GCs); $w_q : V_P \rightarrow [0, 1]$ assigns the read error probability p_{ro} to each qubit; $w_e : E_P \rightarrow [0, 1]$ assigns the CZ gate error probability p_{cz} to each edge.

A layout is defined as an injective function $f : V_L \hookrightarrow V_P$ that preserves adjacency, i.e., $(u, v) \in E_L \implies (f(u), f(v)) \in E_P$. In graph theory, finding a layout is equivalent to finding a subgraph isomorphism of G_L within G_P . Because the general subgraph isomorphism problem is NP-complete, variants of the VF2 algorithm (implemented in rustworkx) are used, accompanied by pruning heuristics: discarding vertices with $w_q > 0.1$ and edges with $w_e > 0.1$, branch width limits, etc.

Once the immersions $f_i : G_L \hookrightarrow G_P$ have been enumerated, a cost function, a total error metric, is defined as

$$\mathcal{E}(f_i) = \sum_{q \in \text{Im}(f_i)} w_q(q) + \sum_{e \in f_i(E_L)} w_e(e). \quad (1.1)$$

The initial layout problem reduces to minimizing $\mathcal{E}(f_i)$ subject to f_i being a subgraph isomorphism.

1.2 Geometric and Noise Limitations on IBM QPUs

Current IBM QPUs primarily employ heavy-hex and heavy-square topologies—deformed variants of a regular square/hexagon intended to reduce cross-coupling errors compared to dense meshes. These architectures impose two fundamental constraints. First, each physical qubit is connected to at most two or three neighbors. Decoupling distant logical interactions requires inserting SWAP chains, increasing the depth, which leads to accelerated decoherence of the system. Second, both $p_{ro}(q)$ and $p_{cz}(e)$ vary. That is, heterogeneous noise is position-dependent.

This shows that the search surface is highly irregular. In fact, certain vertices are forbidden with $w_q > 0.1$, which means that potentially optimal subgraphs within that region cannot be considered solutions. At the same time, the low connectivity of heavy-hex restricts the number of possible isomorphisms. Therefore, the problem should be approached as a costly subgraph isomorphism rather than as a geometric visualization problem.

The algorithm `get_zigzag_physical_layout` [5], [8] takes advantage of this formulation: (i) it generates the zig-zag logical graph parameterized by $|V_L|$ and n_{ancillas} ; (ii) it prunes G_P by eliminating Q_{bad} and E_{bad} ; (iii) it applies VF2 to enumerate feasible dives; and (iv) it chooses the one with minimum cost \mathcal{E} . The following sections formalize each of these steps and demonstrate why the subgraph isomorphism approach offers quantifiable advantages over static heuristics based solely on geometric visual inspection.

Chapter 2

Hardware Modeling as a Graph

2.1 Formal Definition of the Coupling Map

Let \mathcal{B} be an IBM Quantum processor with $N = |V_P|$ qubits. Its coupling map is modeled as the weighted digraph

$$G_P = (V_P, E_P, w_q, w_e, \alpha), \quad (2.1)$$

where $V_P = 0, \dots, N - 1$ is the set of physical qubit identifiers; $E_P \subseteq V_P \times V_P$ is the set of directed edges that specify the pairs (i, j) on which the backend allows a two-qubit gate to be applied—in IBM, typically CX or CZ . The same unoriented pair will be denoted i, j when only connectivity is of interest. $w_q: V_P \rightarrow [0, 1]$ maps the read error rate $p_{ro}(i)$ of each qubit; $w_e: E_P \rightarrow [0, 1]$ maps the two-qubit error rate $p_{2q}(i, j)$. These functions are updated daily using RMS calibrations. Finally, $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^N$ collects additional metadata irrelevant to connectivity (times T_1, T_2 , frequencies, etc.).

The `CouplingMap` class Qiskit implements this structure as a directed graph and provides symmetric closure, subgraph reduction, and distance lookup (BFS) operations that the transpiler uses to insert SWAPs. [4].

A key property is the maximum valency $\Delta(G_P) = \max_{v \in V_P} \deg(v)$, which, for modern IBM topologies, satisfies $\Delta \leq 3$; this bound imposes combinatorial constraints on the search for feasible subgraphs.

2.2 Topological Properties of Heavy-Hex Networks

IBM adopted the heavy-hex lattice starting with Falcon-r4 processors (2021) to mitigate frequency-crowding and cross-coupling errors. [7]. Its construction can be described as follows:

- Start from the regular hexagonal tiling $\mathcal{H} \subset \mathbb{R}^2$.

- Remove the three alternating edges in each hexagon, leaving a "Y" pattern.
- Roll the resulting lattice so that the valence 3 vertices are "heavy" and the valence 2 vertices form linear chains.
- Formally, the graph of a processor with $m \times n$ cells is

$$H_{m,n} = (V_{m,n}, E_{m,n}), \quad \deg_{H_{m,n}}(v) \in \{2, 3\}. \quad (2.2)$$

Property	Value in heavy-hex	Compilation consequence
Planarity	$H_{m,n}$ is planar	Allows visualization of routes without crossings; useful for geometric heuristics.
Maximum valency	$\Delta = 3$	Limits the parallelization bandwidth of 2-qubit gates.
Diameter	$\text{diam}(H_{m,n}) = \Theta(m + n)$	Penalizes distant logical interactions, implying more SWAPs.
Treewidth	$\text{tw}(H_{m,n}) = \Theta(\sqrt{N})$	Sets a lower bound on circuit depth after exact partitioning.
Girth	$g = 6$ (length of minimal cycles)	Favors error-correcting codes based on hexagonal faces.

Table 2.1 Structural characteristics of the heavy-hex graph and their implications for quantum compilation.

Spatial noise heterogeneity is superimposed on this geometry: qubits at heavy vertices typically exhibit slightly lower p_{2q} errors due to more uniform couplings, while chain qubits (valence 2) show lower dispersion in p_{ro} [6]. These error gradients induce a functional asymmetry: it is advantageous to map the highest centrality logical qubits (according to the logical graph) to valence 3 vertices, reserving valence 2 vertices for ancillas or qubits with low participation in two-qubit interactions.

In the Heron family of processors, IBM has refined heavy-hex to incorporate selective three-way bonding, but the average valence remains ≤ 3 in order to preserve the frequency isolation benefits [3].

Chapter 3

Mathematical construction of the zig-zag pattern

3.1 Linear chains α - α : graph G_{lin}

We start with two independent linear chains (one per α spin channel of each orbital):

$$\begin{aligned} P_n^{(A)} &= (A_0, A_1, \dots, A_{n-1}), \\ P_n^{(B)} &= (B_0, B_1, \dots, B_{n-1}), \quad n = \text{num_orbitals}. \end{aligned}$$

Each chain is a P_n path graph with $|V(P_n)| = n$ and $|E(P_n)| = n - 1$.

It is then defined

$$G_{\text{lin}} = P_n^{(A)} \sqcup P_n^{(B)},$$

the disjoint union of both chains. The code `create_linear_chains` [5], [8] implements exactly this construction, adding the nodes A_k ($0 \leq k < n$), the nodes B_k ($n \leq k < 2n$) and the edges (A_k, A_{k+1}) , (B_k, B_{k+1}) . In G_{lin} all internal vertices have $\text{deg} = 2$ and the edge vertices $\text{deg} = 1$; this guarantees $\Delta(G_{\text{lin}}) = 2 \leq \Delta(G_P)$ for any heavy-hex backend ($\Delta = 3$), a necessary condition for embedding.

3.2 Connection qubits α - β and parameter n_{ancillas}

To capture the α - β interactions, i.e. spin jumps, C_k connection qubits are added that link both chains and generate the zig-zag motif. Analytically, let

$$K_t = \{k \in \mathbb{N} \mid 0 \leq k < t, k \equiv 0 \pmod{4}\},$$

where $t \leq n$ is the number of positions inspected. For each $k \in K_t$ a new node C_k is introduced and the edges

$$(A_k, C_k), \quad (C_k, B_k).$$

The total number of α - β qubits is

$$m(t) = |K_t| = \left\lfloor \frac{t+3}{4} \right\rfloor.$$

The algorithm `create_lucj_zigzag_layout` sequentially adds these nodes and edges while checking, via `rustworkx.is_subgraph_isomorphic`, whether the resulting graph is embeddable in the coupling map; when the test fails, it reduces t and retries, returning the largest admissible t and the value $m(t) = \text{num_alpha_beta_qubits}$.

The parameter n_{ancillas} included in `get_zigzag_physical_layout` increments $|V(P_n^{(A)})|$ and $|V(P_n^{(B)})|$ to $n + n_{\text{ancillas}}$; Conceptually, this corresponds to dead extensions at the end of each chain where auxiliary qubits (scratch space) can be placed without altering the main couplings.

3.3 Embeddability conditions in the physical topology

Let $G_{\text{zig}}(t)$ be the graph resulting from inserting $m(t)$ connection qubits. For a feasible initial mapping to exist, it is necessary and sufficient that

$$\exists f : V(G_{\text{zig}}) \hookrightarrow V_P \quad \text{s.t.} \quad (u, v) \in E(G_{\text{zig}}) \Rightarrow (f(u), f(v)) \in E_P,$$

that is, $G_{\text{zig}}(t)$ is an isomorphic subgraph of G_P . This imposes three structural restrictions:

- $\max_{v \in V(G_{\text{zig}})} \deg v = 3$ (nodes A_k, B_k with $k \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$), compatible with the heavy-hex bound $\Delta(G_P) = 3$.
- Every pair (A_k, B_k) linked via C_k must be admitted as a path of length 2 in G_P , that is, there must exist a vertex $q \in V_P$ such that $(f(A_k), q), (q, f(B_k)) \in E_P$. In heavy-hex, these bridges are available every four longitudinal steps, which motivates the $k \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$ pattern.
- $|V(G_{\text{zig}}(t))| = 2(n + n_{\text{ancillas}}) + m(t) \leq |V_P|$. For backends of 127 qubits or less, this inequality forces practical limits of n and m .

The iterative procedure of `create_lucj_zigzag_layout` ensures that these conditions are satisfied: it starts with $t = n$ (bridge in every fourth orbital) and decreases t until the maximum embeddable graph is found, thus ensuring the highest possible α - β coupling without violating the heavy-hex geometry.

The result is a zig-zag pattern that, by construction, preserves the logical locality of the original problem and keeps the degree of each node within physical boundaries, thus minimizing the need for SWAPs and exposure to noise in actual execution.

Chapter 4

Subgraph Isomorphism: Formulation and Algorithm

When we search for an optimal initial layout, we are, in essence, trying to fit the logical graph G_{zig} —of low valency but long length—into the physical graph G_P that describes the heavy-hex topology. This task is naturally formalized as a subgraph isomorphism problem.

4.1 Definition and Notation

Let $G_1 = (V_1, E_1)$ and $G_2 = (V_2, E_2)$ be two graphs, with directed or undirected edges as appropriate. We say that G_1 is an isomorphic subgraph of G_2 if there exists an injective $f : V_1 \hookrightarrow V_2$ such that for every $(u, v) \in E_1$ the following holds: $(f(u), f(v)) \in E_2$. When it is required that every edge present between the image vertices also appears in E_1 , we speak of an induced isomorphism; in IBM Quantum, the non-induced variant is sufficient, because the extra edges of the coupling map never harm the execution.

With this notation, finding a valid layout is equivalent to finding a function f as described. If, in addition, we associate costs with vertices and edges, we can select among all the isomorphisms the one that minimizes $\mathcal{E}(f)$, the total error metric introduced in Section 1.1 Eq. (1.1).

4.2 Computational Complexity

The subgraph isomorphism problem is NP-complete for general graphs: it contains both Clique and Hamiltonian Path as special cases. [2]. Unlike pure graph isomorphism—whose exact position in the complexity hierarchy remains open despite Babai’s quasi-polynomial algorithm—the sub version remains firmly in the NP-complete category even for dense bipartite graphs, and its exact baseline algorithms scale exponentially in the worst case. For small instances or with favorable structural

properties (low valency, large degree dispersion), backtracking-type algorithms with smart pruning are very effective in practice.

4.3 Portraiting the VF2 Algorithm in Rustworkx

IBM Quantum and Qiskit use the rustworkx library as their algorithmic engine. Their implementation of the VF2 algorithm—originally by Cordella et al. [1]—is exposed to Python via the functions `is_subgraph_isomorphic` and, crucially, `vf2_mapping`, which returns an iterator over all possible immersions [10], [9].

VF2 traverses a search tree where each node represents a partial pair (M, T) , where M is the vertex-to-vertex partial mapping and T is the candidate boundary. In each expansion, a free vertex from G_1 is selected and its assignment is tested on each compatible vertex in G_2 . Two types of feasibility rules prune the space:

- The number of already matched preimages is checked to respect future adjacency—a refined version of the degree test that provides topological consistency checking.
- rustworkx allows passing matcher callbacks for nodes and edges. In our flow, these callbacks immediately discard qubits with $p_{ro} > 0.1$ or links with $p_{cz} > 0.1$, so that the exploration never descends to a state that would violate noise thresholds.

Invoking `vf2_mapping(G_{zig} , G_P , ...)` returns a generator of f_i mappings. Each one is scored with the $\mathcal{E}(f_i)$ function, and in practice, it only takes a few hundred immersions to identify the minimum cost thanks to the combination of attribute pruning and the inherent sparsity of heavy-hex. Rustworkx’s adaptation of VF2 transforms an NP-complete problem into a feasible procedure for the current size of IBM QPUs, provided that appropriate error and valence filters are applied.

Chapter 5

Enumeration of Isomorphic Immersions

Once the logical graph G_{zig} and the physical graph G_P have been established, the task moves from theory to practice: enumerating all injective mappings $f : V(G_{\text{zig}}) \hookrightarrow V(G_P)$ that preserve adjacencies. The `utils.py` [8] module delegates this search to the `rustworkx.vf2_mapping` routine, whose implementation is an optimized VF2-type backtracking in Rust.

5.1 Exhaustive Search with `vf2_mapping`

In `get_zigzag_physical_layout`, a symmetric, duplicate-free version of the coupling map is first prepared (`_make_backend_cmap_pygraph`) and the maximum admissible zigzag is constructed (`create_lucj_zigzag_layout`). With both graphs ready, the call

```
isomorphic_mappings = rustworkx.vf2_mapping(  
    backend_coupling_graph, G, subgraph=True  
)
```

returns a lazy generator that produces one by one all subgraph isomorphisms between G_{zig} and G_P . VF2 maintains two boundary lists—one in the pattern, one in the host—and expands compatible assignments; each decision is filtered in $O(1)$ time with simple degree and label tests. The additional pruning performed in the construction phase (eliminating qubits and edges with error > 0.1) decreases branching, and in practice, the number of dives typically drops to a few dozen on 133 qubit Heron processors. Even so, the enumeration is exhaustive: the algorithm explores the entire search tree to the bottom, ensuring that no valid realization is missed.

5.2 Translating Mappings to Physical Layouts

Each element of the generator is a dictionary $q_{\text{phys}} \mapsto q_{\text{virt}}$. To convert it into the list understood by the transpiler, the dictionary is traversed and the physical image is stored in the position corresponding to the virtual index:

```
initial_layout = [None] * (2 * (num_orbitals + num_ancillas) + num_alpha_beta_qubits)
for physical, virtual in mapping.items():
    initial_layout[virtual] = physical
```

The resulting list first contains the vertices of both α - α chains, then the possible α - β connection qubits. Since the latter do not participate directly in the LUCJ ansatz, they are pruned at the end of the process:

```
return layout[:-num_alpha_beta_qubits], num_alpha_beta_qubits
```

returning only the $2n$ operational qubits.

To decide which of all the enumerated layouts is optimal, an empirical error metric is applied. `lightweight_layout_error_scoring` traverses the lists, sums the error probability of each measurement and each CZ gate, and imposes infinite penalties when the layout touches any qubit or link marked as unacceptable. Since this scoring is monotonically additive, it is sufficient to sort the results and take the first list. The procedure thus retains the logical exhaustiveness of VF2, but limits the total cost to traversing and scoring only the few hundred dips that pass the topological filters.

Chapter 6

Filtering Infeasible Layouts

The VF2 enumerator produces a set $\mathcal{F} = f_1, f_2, \dots$ of immersions that meet only the topological requirement, i.e., being a subgraph. Before assessing their quality, it is advisable to discard those that, even if geometrically correct, would exploit device components with unacceptable fidelity. The filtering is based on two empirical thresholds—0.1 for readout and 0.1 for CZ gates—that correspond to the threshold probability beyond which error events dominate the statistical variance of data collection in quantum chemistry tasks with moderate shot repetition ($\approx .10000$ shots).

6.1 Definition of the set Q_{bad}

Let $w_q: V_P \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be the daily read error rate of the backend. We define

$$Q_{\text{bad}} = \{q \in V_P \mid w_q(q) \geq 0.1\}. \quad (6.1)$$

Fig. 6.1 Coupling map of the IBM Torino quantum processor. Black nodes indicate `bad_readout_qubits` qubits with a readout error ≥ 0.1 . Red edges represent `bad_czgate_edges`, two-qubit connections with a CZ gate error ≥ 0.1 .

These qubits appear black in the coupling map visualization and are excluded from further evaluation. In the `lightweight_layout_error_scoring` code, the instruction

```
if any(q in bad_readout_qubits for q in layout):
    continue
```

exactly implements the condition $f(V_{\text{zig}}) \cap Q_{\text{bad}} = \emptyset$. The statement `continue` causes the layout to never be scored and therefore cannot win.

6.2 Definition of the set E_{bad}

Similarly, if $w_e: E_P \rightarrow [0, 1]$ denotes the CZ gate error, then it is defined

$$E_{\text{bad}} = \{e \in E_P \mid w_e(e) \geq 0.1\}.$$

The edges of E_{bad} are shown in red on the physical graph. In programmatic filtering, each logical pair $(u, v) \in E_{\text{zig}}$ is translated into a physical pair $(f(u), f(v))$; if that image belongs to E_{bad} (in either orientation, to cover directed graphs), the layout is discarded:

```
physical_edge = (layout[edge[0]], layout[edge[1]])
if physical_edge in bad_czgate_edges or physical_edge[::-1] in bad_czgate_edges:
    skip = True
```

and the loop abandons the iteration.

6.3 Joint Effect of Filtering

Let $G'_P = (V'_P, E'_P)$ with $V'_P = V_P \setminus Q_{\text{bad}}$ and $E'_P = E_P \setminus E_{\text{bad}}$. Interpreted at the level of graph theory, filtering is equivalent to replacing the original host G_P with the induced subgraph G'_P before evaluating the error metric. However, to avoid making combinatorial search more expensive, the code preserves G_P during enumeration and applies a posteriori pruning in the scoring phase: the first strategy guarantees exhaustiveness, the second maintains performance. The result is that only those mappings f_i whose rank is contained in V'_P and whose edge images elude E_{bad} move on to the sorting stage by the $\mathcal{E}(f_i)$ metric. Filtering by Q_{bad} and E_{bad} not only protects the user from extremely noisy regions: it also reduces the score dispersion, allowing the fine error metric < 0.1 to discriminate more sensitively between viable layouts.

Chapter 7

Cost Function and Selection Heuristic

Once the layouts that touch banned qubits or couplings have been filtered out, the algorithm still needs a criterion to choose the best of the surviving immersions. This choice is governed by the metric

$$\varepsilon_{\text{total}} = \sum_{e \in E_{\text{virt}}} \varepsilon_{2q}(f(e)) + \sum_{q \in V_{\text{virt}}} \varepsilon_{\text{meas}}(f(q)), \quad (7.1)$$

where f is the physical dip, E_{virt} and V_{virt} are the edges and vertices of the logical zig-zag, ε_{2q} is the error probability of the CZ gate on the corresponding physical edge, and $\varepsilon_{\text{meas}}$ is the readout error of each physical qubit. The function `lightweight_layout_error_scoring` implements exactly this summation: it accumulates `total_2q_error` over all virtual edges and adds it to `total_measurement_error`, which aggregates the readout rates of each qubit in the layout.

7.1 Monotonicity and Practical Consequences

The metric (7.1) is additive monotonic: if a new element is introduced—for example, because the number of orbitals increases or an additional edge is forced—the cost can never decrease, since all contributions are nonnegative. This property allows for two optimizations:

- as soon as the partial cost of the assignment exceeds the best value found, the branch is discarded.
- layouts for n orbitals can be constructed from the optimal $n - 1$ solution by adding a pair of vertices and recalculating only the new contributions, avoiding repeating previous computations.

7.2 Normalization and Comparability

Because $\varepsilon_{\text{total}}$ grows linearly with the graph size, its absolute value is only comparable between circuits with the same number of vertices and edges. Normalized versions are introduced to compare devices or interfaces of different lengths.

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_{\text{edge}} = \frac{1}{|E_{\text{virt}}|} \sum_{e \in E_{\text{virt}}} \varepsilon_{2q}(f(e)), \quad \bar{\varepsilon}_{\text{qubit}} = \frac{1}{|V_{\text{virt}}|} \sum_{q \in V_{\text{virt}}} \varepsilon_{\text{meas}}(f(q)),$$

and their linear combination is weighted with weights that reflect the sensitivity of the final algorithm to two-qubit errors versus measurement errors. Furthermore, nothing prevents replacing the probabilities p with fidelities $F = 1 - p$ to obtain a multiplicative metric, but the additive form simplifies the search for minima, and in the $p \ll 1$ regime, both approximations differ only in terms of second order.

Chapter 8

Conclusions

The presented strategy reinterprets the choice of initial layout as an exact cost subgraph isomorphism problem. Starting from a zig-zag logical pattern suitable for LUCJ ansatz, the algorithm:

1. Models the backend topology as an error-weighted graph.
2. Iteratively builds the logical graph and checks its embeddability using VF2.
3. Enumerates all immersions, discards those that touch qubits or couplings with error ≥ 0.1 , and scores the remaining ones with a linear noise metric.
4. Selects the minimum-cost layout, ensuring optimality within the isomorphic space.

Chapter 9

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